

Open Reviews is a good first step. Pseudo-Anonymous Reviews can take it further.

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Nature journal [recently announced](#) that all their reviews will be henceforth open. This is a good first step that will hopefully extend to other journals in Springer Nature as well as other major publishers. It will go a long way in improving trust in Science. They will also allow reviewers to choose to be anonymous. Blind peer review is one of the pillars of the publication system and the choice of reviewers needs to be respected.

However, there have been a lot of reported cases where [reviewers abuse this anonymity](#) to ask for citations to their own articles, sometimes not even related to the paper being reviewed. Increasingly, [a lot of reviews are also done by AI](#), leading to low quality feedback.

To mitigate these issues, one can make the reviews Pseudo-Anonymous, i.e. the reviews should be traceable. Research integrity teams can then verify the bad 'actors'. It will also act as a deterrent for people providing shoddy, lazy or unfair reviews.

Additionally, it will help provide useful analytics for both editors as well as readers and help them take more informed decisions.

How will this work?

Consider a reviewer called Jamie. He/she can review multiple papers. Each review, which will be open, will contain a different pseudonym to ensure the anonymity of the reviewer. This is what is going to happen already with open peer reviews.

We propose that while the reviews remain anonymous to the public, the publisher still maintains a secure database which contains all the reviews by Jamie. This database should not be accessible to even editors. Only people with access to this highly classified database should be the research integrity teams.

Fig 1 - Proposed Framework to ensure anonymity of reviewer as well as enable traceability

How will this help?

There are multiple benefits of the proposed framework :

1) **Deterrent against lazy and malevolent reviewers:** It will help publishers to be able to analyze (perhaps automatically) all the reviews by a person. If a reviewer is copy-pasting his reviews or consistently soliciting citations, then the pattern can be easily recognized by AI and flagged to the publisher. It can also help editors and publishers find reviewers who might be reviewing prolifically, perhaps with the help of AI generated reviews.

2) **Increase fairness by normalizing the reviews:** It will also help reduce inconsistency in the review process as different reviewers can have different scales. It makes comparison of reviews difficult. In the proposed framework, one can normalize the reviewers score with the average score they give. This will also help make the review process fairer and less prone to vagaries of reviewers.

Thanks to pseudo-anonymity, editors as well as readers can find out the average statistics for the reviewers and make a more informed decision.

Fig 2 – Reviewer analytics available to the editor. For average readers, the name will be anonymized.

3) **Provide incentives to reviewers by giving them credit:** It is becoming increasingly difficult to find reviewers as they do not gain anything out of reviewing. A centralized database will help publishers reward reviewers who help keep the system functional.

Potential issues.

Some possible issues with such a system is that it will still not address reviews across different publishers. Hopefully in the future, the publishers can coordinate amongst themselves to create a common database for profiles of different reviewers. In any case, this is still much better than complete anonymity where even two editors of journals of the same publishing house will not be able to compare notes.

A centralized database does increase the chances of data leaks. Any system developed will need to have adequate protection like encrypted storage of details in the database so that even in case of leaks, there is not much harm. Such secure and robust solutions already exist and are regularly used by internet companies who store sensitive user data.

If implemented, this solution will improve the trust in science even further as well as help catch lazy or ill-intentioned reviewers using the peer-review system to game citations or increase their influence by reviewing prolifically.

Lost Opportunity: The Invisible cost of lost Peer Review

Now, consider what happens when a manuscript is rejected after the first round of peer review. The intellectual effort invested by reviewers is effectively lost — an especially frustrating reality for academics who volunteer their time and expertise for free.

While some publishers offer manuscript transfer options within their journal portfolios, the accompanying peer reviews are often not reused. In a few cases, authors may revise and improve their manuscripts based on the feedback, which is at least a partial gain. However, more often than not, those reviews go unused. The current system can help count those reviews.

[One study](#) found that even with a rejection rate of just 50%, around 97% of papers eventually get published — typically by the fifth round, after four resubmissions. Even with a high rejection rate of 90%, about 41% of papers still make it to publication after four attempts.

This shows how much of peer review efforts get wasted — intellectual contributions are lost with every cycle, and the time of reviewers is repeatedly taken up by evaluating similar versions of the same manuscript.

Future possibilities

Peer review system is a pillar, if not the bedrock of science. It is important that it is not abused. Given the exponential rise in retracted articles and increasing use of AI for generating reviews, it becomes paramount that the reviews are more systematic and face greater scrutiny.

We hope that Nature and other publishers extend open peer review to all their journals, including mega journals like Scientific Reports. In an ideal world, the publishers should be able to coordinate amongst each other to improve the efficiency of reviews and keep a closer watch on bad actor reviewers using the proposed framework.

We welcome any feedback and potential pitfalls of the proposed system that we might have overlooked.